

Original Article

A Study of Impact of Job Stress on Employee Turnover and Emotional Exhaustion in Public and Private Sector of Peshawar

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Abstract

In today's era for achieving success and productivity, one should cope with job stress. Job stress is the experience of lack of equilibrium between demands at the job or workplace and a worker's ability to cope with these demands (Ullrich, 1990). Job stress has an influence on both the employee and the organization. That is why it is considered as a very important matter of work place. And for the same reason this research is based on revealing the impact of job stress on employee's two type of behaviours which are employee turnover and emotional exhaustion. A questionnaire consisting of sixteen item measuring all the scales is prepared for finding the impact of job stress on employee turnover and emotional exhaustion with the help of regression analysis. Datum is collected from 121 respondents of 5 organization of Peshawar. Out of these 5 organizations 2 are from government sector and 3 are from private sector of Peshawar Pakistan. It is shown by the results that a very significant relationship is present between the research variables. Positive relationship is found between job stress and employee turnover. Positive relationship is also found between job stress and emotional exhaustion. However this positive relationship is stronger in private organizations as compare to public organizations. Standard sources are followed for selection of scales and instruments. The research results are of great importance and value for a large number of organizations especially for management departments in order to understand the employee behaviours and are also important for the betterment of both the employee and the organization.

Keywords: Job Stress, Employee Turnover, Emotional Exhaustion, Public and Private Sector, Peshawar

Introduction

As Pakistan is a developing country its business and economy is also developing. The human resource of Pakistan is playing a very vital role in this business development hence an ever growing and developing economy provides ideal background for research on the topic of impact of job stress on employee turnover and emotional exhaustion.

At work place stress is a very important factor. Stress occur in many different ways in diverse working conditions and also influences the workers in different ways. Job stress is being studied in different situations for having a deep understanding of it and in order to diminish its negative outcomes on employees' performance and behaviour and their behaviour towards job commitment and turnover. Stress is a multi-dimensional concept it can be defined on the basis of organizational view point and language (Abdalla et al., 2024; Ahmed S. et al, 2014). The term 'stress' is used to show the feeling of inability to cope, experience of fatigue and deviation from normal functioning due to change in conditions. State of being at non equilibrium due to demands of the job at workplace and the worker's ability to cope with these demands is occupational stress (Ullrich, 1990). Anxiety and nervous tension are not stress. Some similar term of stress are strain, burnout and conflict. Stress is sometimes healthy like a person having stress due to challenge, or due to starting new job, having promotions all have insight stress but that stress lead to improvement (Zada et al., 2024; Luthans, 2010). And this is known as

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'*eustress or pressure*' in literature. Stress which is dysfunctional and does not leads to improvement rather it lower downs the performance is known as 'distress' (Khan et al., 2024; Mahr, 2010).

Employee turnover means the rate at which employees of an organization leaves the job and are replaced (Ruth, 2014). While experience of imbalance by an employee between efforts spent on his work and rewards obtained, creates emotional exhaustion (Zada et al., 2024; Bakker et al. 2000). Job stress had an influence on employee turnover, and emotional exhaustion and on many others. Stress plays a very significant role in employees behaviour related to job like turnover (Zada et al., 2024; Sager, 1994). Sabine S, (2001) found a positive relation between emotional exhaustion of employees at workplace and job stress.

This study thus examines the impact of job stress among the employees of the public and private sectors of Peshawar. Hence it examines the influence of job stress on employee turnover and emotional exhaustion, thus, accessing the relationship between them.

The next section presents the literature review and hypothesis building. Then the next section to literature review presents the research method, research design, sample taken and methods used, tools for computing results. Lastly there is discussion on the basis of results the impact of research variable in both sectors are also discussed separately, practical implication, limitations and future recommendations.

Literature Review and Hypothesis Building

Job Stress

Stress is a familiar and very vast concept, which is used for giving explanation to different mental (psychological and physiological) pressures in the lives of human beings. In fact this era is known as the era of stress and anxiety (Coleman, 1976) and it is very difficult to stay stress free. 'Heaven' is the one and only place in this great universe which is stress free according to the Holy Qur'an. Stress is not confined to working class only. People who does not work and are not professionals also experience stress. Here we have considered job stress only. Stress which is experienced by working class only.

What is Stress?

Job stress can be defined as the experience of having negative mental, emotional and physical responses by and individual manifested when there is a mismatch between the requirements of the job and the needs of the worker. It is also an experience of lacking the capability or lacking resources for performing job, hence stress is an out force that has influence over inner feelings (Khan at al., 2024; NIOSH 2014). Everyone knows that job stress is a result of interaction between worker and working conditions. Stress is physical, mental or emotional response when these working conditions are acting as a source for an individual's mental and physical tension (M. Ramachandran, 2011). Many of the researchers had defined stress in different ways most of the time the term stress is used to show the feeling of inability to cope, experience of fatigue and deviation from normal functioning due to change in conditions. State of being at non equilibrium due to pressures of the work and work place and a worker's ability to cope with these demands and pressures is occupational stress (Khan et al., 2024; Ullrich, 1990). Hens Selye (1950) redefined stress as rate of wear and tear on the body.

In literature Conservation of Resources Theory (COR) explains stress in this way that individuals always seeks to preserve, renew and enhance their resources and having failure in doing this leads to stress. Where resources are defined as objective personal conditions, energies or characteristics which contribute to achieve or preserve valued resources. COR is an integrative stress theory because it includes both the worker's attitude and perception towards stress and external environmental sources as well. The main gist of this theory is that as work demands exceed the bounds of official job, they rob the many resources of worker which are required to fulfil formal job, leaving the worker with fewer resources which in turn increase the stress and leads to burnout.

In literature researchers have used job stress and occupational stress synonymously. Jamal in 2005 defined job stress as reaction of any individual to the threatening characteristics in the working environment. Stress cannot be considered as an outcome of pressure, rather it is a perception of pressure (Zada et al., 2024; Ahmed. S et al., 2014).

What is Not Stress?

Now a day's workplace stress has become a major problem for human resource managers. Up till now the discussion was about what is stress. But now the discussion is about what is not a stress like simple anxiety is not stress. Stress is accompanied with anxiety so stress and anxiety are not the same and they cannot be equated.

Like anxiety, nervous tension can be a result of stress, but they are not the same things (Ullah et al., 2024; Luthans, 2010). Sometimes challenge is also confused with stress but they are not the same because challenge is a thing which energizes us psychologically, physically and motivates us to learn new things for achieving that challenge and after its achievement we feel relax and satisfied (NIOSH 2014).

Similar Terms

Stress, burnout and conflict are similar terms. Stress and conflict have conceptual differences but functionally they are the same. Both have functional and dysfunctional outcomes. Low level of stress and conflict are functional. While burnout begins when the ability to cope stress lets down. Stress is sometimes healthy like a person having stress due to challenge, or due to starting new job, having promotions all have insight stress but that stress lead to improvement (Luthans, 2010). And this is known as 'eustress or pressure' in literature. Stress which is dysfunctional and does not leads to improvement rather it lower downs the performance is known as 'distress' (Saeed et al., 2024; Mahr, 2010).

Stressors or Sources of Stress

A large number of researcher have identified that at workplace psychosocial demands are important stressors. By social stressors it means that those incidents which are social in nature but promotes strain like task difficulty, conflict, unfair attitude at workplace and incompatible expectations (Dormann, Zaph 2004). Job stress can be from different sources, not always from inside of the organization rather from outside too. Stress can be due to socio demographic predicators like age, gender, level of education (Purcell, 2011). These sources are outside the environment of organization. Organizational stress sources include poor resources, less wages, high monotony, too much supervision and responsibility and too little autonomy, no or less social concern, job insecurity, no or less opportunities for advancement, and obsolete management styles (Khan et al., 2024; Schmitz, 2000). Stress is different for different individuals for example stress on fresh employees or trainees is fear of losing job because of incapability while old employees do not experience such stress.

In the employee's view, the main reasons for their stress are technological change, lack of communication, role ambiguity, mistake or failure, looming deadlines, angry boss and cantankerous clients (Khattak et al., 2023; Ranjith, 2011). The sources of stress differ from one person to another, what is stress for one individual may not be for others.

In the same way sources of stress differ as we move across different professional. Like sources of stress in employees of school is due to high workload, long working hours, less cooperative attitude among teachers, and having concern about the education and wedding of their daughters rather than having concern about their jobs (Malik & Din, 2000-2001). According to the research conducted by Style and Cavanaugh (1996) on stress, they revealed some variables as major sources of stress like work expectations, concern for fulfilling own needs, relationship of student and teacher, relationship between peers, conflicts between peers due to different backgrounds as the sources of stress. They also commented that ego and professional hurdles were sources of stress among teachers. Dean (1995) reported that stress in teachers is also caused by the environment in which they are working, poor working condition creates stress. If any teacher is not cleared about the roles and duties and expected performance then it results in job stress, or if the management by the school heads is not effective or behaviour of children is poor then it leads to stress. Stress in school heads is due to greater responsibility as they have to interact with public and with higher authorities as well and they have to look after all other things as well. Similarly for nurses the major job stress predicators can be the health condition of the patient and patient's low level of satisfaction with the efforts made by their immediate nurse (S. Stordeur, 2000). Sources of stress for physicians are a bit unique from other professions and that us they have to deal with illness and death on daily basis and when a patient is not cured, they feels a sense of failure and fear of lawsuits for medical malpractice (Zada et al., 2023; Aharon et al., 2015)

Robins (2010) have mentioned all the sources or causes of job stress into four categories, the above mentioned/discussed stressors are also covered in the discussion below:

Extra organizational: Stressors include changes in technology and societal trends, relationship with family and friends, economic and financial position, race and gender.

Organizational Stressors: include administrative policies and procedures, working environment, working hours, conflict, monitoring system and more specifically organizational stressors include lack of clear job description

and reporting relationships, responsibility without authority, inability to voice complaints and inadequate recognition.

Group stressors: includes stress from the experience of lack of group cohesiveness and lack of social support.

Individual Stressors: Individual stressors are based on the personality of an individual some people have more personal control and some do not. Like some people gets stressed more than others.

The stress caused by these factors have deleterious effects on the individual and the organization and society as well. But low level of stress and conflict can enhance the performance of employees. The relationship of stress and job performance is effected by the nature of task and individual personality type. As the level of stress gets high, it becomes dysfunctional and drops the performance sharply. Employees experiencing job stress are less motivated, unhealthy and less productive (Nasrin & Hojat, 2013).

Problems due to stress include physical problems, psychological problems and behavioural problems. Physical problems are recognized by having weak immune system, hypertension and heart diseases, headaches, back pain, and digestive disorder.

Psychological problems include anxiety, anger, nervousness, depression, tension, boredom and irritability, sabotage, lowered self-esteem, resentment of supervision and job dissatisfaction.

Behavioural problems due to job stress include overeating, sleeplessness, increased smoking and drinking and abuse of drugs (Scanlon, 1986; Patton and Questell, 1988).

All the problems costs a lot to the company. Not only in form of low productivity but also by cost from medical allowances of the employees. And in form of absentees and turnover of workers (Luthans, 2010).

Employee Turnover

Employees are a source of competitive advantage for the organization. In fact human capital runs all the others factors of production efficiently. Human resource enables the organizations to enjoy significant profits. In fact human resource is the most important and valuable asset of an organization. Organizations in all over the world have realized that talented workforce is the key to betterment and human resource managers are trying to retain potential employees. But now a days the employees are leaving the organization frequently. Which is causing different problems and costs to the organization. High employee turnover is posing the problem of labour shortage and increasing cost at firm level, which is a danger for long term sustainability of the industry (Kuruville & Ranganathan, 2010). Turnover is an index of a company's effectiveness and some understanding of the company itself. And also the information about turnover helps in planning, predicting and controlling of resources (Shamsuzzoha et al. 2006)

Naumann discussed that turnover and turnover intention are two different phenomenon he defined that turnover is an actual withdrawal of an employee from the organization whereas turnover intention is a conscious willingness of an employee to withdraw from his job (Tor, 1997). Turnover intention is also defined as intention of an employee to find employment with another employer within the next year (Medina, 2012). Employee turnover means the rate at which employees of an organization leave the organization and are replaced (Ruth, 2014). In this paper employee turnover and employee's intention to turnover are used interchangeably because this is the variable that immediately precedes actual employee turnover (Lambert et al. 2001).

Ali in 2013 had discussed that turnover is not always an employee's willingness to leave the organization i.e. voluntary turnover rather sometimes it is involuntary i.e. employers do the termination, dismissals. These are done in response to correct the errors done at the time of recruitment. So that is why involuntary turnover is not much harmful for organizations while voluntary turnover is the loss of potential employee and hence much harmful (Koys DJ, 2001). In involuntary turnover employers can do the termination of non-serious and incompatible or the employee can also terminate the employees in the form of retirement because of old age, less productivity other related issues. Other than these cases of involuntary turnover death is also considered as involuntary turnover (Des & Shaw, 2001). Although turnover is of different types but the basic definition is the same that turnover occurs when employment relation comes to an end (Ruth, 2014).

Rate of turnover is different from one region to the other, it is different for different sectors as well for example private sectors experience high turnover than public sector. It is also dependent upon the economic conditions of that area. If better job opportunities are easily available then the turnover rate will be high. Employees also leave a job or intend to leave a job because of job dissatisfaction (Shamsuzzoha et al. 2006). Either the rate of turnover

is high or low, or turnover is voluntary or involuntary the effects and after effects of turnover are always very important to consider specially from employer point of view because when an employee leaves the a job, the cost which was initially incurred by the employer over his recruitment is lost, then in order to replace him/her they employer needs to do recruitment again which is again a burden on employer (Dalton, Todor & Krackhardt, 1982). Not only the selecting and recruiting cost are incurred again but also the new hire person needs training again and time for learning and in that time period his production is also low so employer bears a lot of burden due to turnover. Turnover also reduces the morale of other employees as well and hence there is a loss of social capital (Des & Shaw 2001). In this way the productivity of other employees also gets down. And for the same reason most of the researchers have argued that it is very difficult to measure the cost of employee turnover, and impossible if the employee who left the job was a skilful performer (Des & Shaw, 2001).

Employee turnover also gives loss to a company in form of transfer of knowledge and experience of employee and transfer of confidential information of the company to outside business environment.

Employee turnover and attrition are sometimes refer for the same things but there is a difference between both. Both are same to some extend like in both cases workforce is reduced but in case of turn over the position vacant is soon filled or replaced but in case of attrition the vacant position is not filled rather that designation or position is eliminated (Mark, 2014).

Emotional Exhaustion

As discussed earlier burnout is used as synonym to stress in literature. And emotional exhaustion is referred as one of the dimensions of burnout (Sabine. S, et al. 2001). The other two dimension are depersonalization and personal accomplishments. The very initial step of burning out process is known as emotional exhaustion (Cordes & Dougherty 1993, Lee & Ashforth 1993). The final stage of burnout known as emotional exhaustion come into existence when employees feel emotionally drained, exhausted, tensed and overwhelmed from their job (Maslach, 1981; Griffin, Hogan, Lambert, et al., 2010). The feeling of an employee having non equilibrium between the efforts which he/she spends at work and the rewards which he obtains in return, creates emotional exhaustion (Bakker et al. 2000). At workplace emotional exhaustion is defined as experience of being drained out due to responsibilities of a job. Emotional exhaustion is an extreme form of work related stress and strain (M.Owais, 2015)

While discussing the productivity of emotionally exhausted employees Mulki et, al said that these kind of employees feel more tiredness and are so tensed that they cannot concentrate on work hence they are less productive and spent less effort on work and they are also non cooperative with others (Mulki, Jaramillo & Locander, 2006). Emotional exhaustion is also created from constant exposure to stress and increasing job demands which continuously weakens emotional and physical states of employees (Zohar, 1997). Emotional exhaustion is a reduction in the emotional and physical responsiveness of an employee due to increasing job demands, personal demands and due to constant stress by Wright in June 1998. Emotional exhaustion causes loss of trust, feeling of concern, spirit and interest in job (Maslach, 1982) Emotional exhaustion is same as ordinary state of physical exertion but due to its widespread qualities it is more persistent (Griffith, Kerr, Mayo, & Topal, 1950). Exertion for long time creates physical illness and an employee having physical health ill, creates emotional exhaustion (Bartely & Chute, 1947)

In past, emotional exhaustion is being studied as an outcome variable but in some researches it is also incorporated as predicator or contributing variable (Roy & Avdija, 2012; Saiphon, 2010; Mohler & Byrne, 2004). Emotional exhaustion can be studied independently and can also be studied in conjunction with other variables because as emotional exhaustion is a dimension of burnout so it is being used to measure two other dimensions of burnout so for this reason it has the ability of acting independently and dependently (Maslach, 1982).

Sources of emotional exhaustion vary from organization to organization for example high workload and lack of social support from supervisor and lack of advancement opportunities (Lee and Ashforth, 1996) lack of training and skills require to satisfactorily deal with the task assigned (Maslach and Pines, 1977), lack of adequate pay, excessive stress, demand for perfection, lack of recognition and underemployment. High workload is consistently related to emotional exhaustion in literature. Morris and Feldman (1997) also considered that as frequency of interpersonal communication with clients increases the expectation to lead to emotional exhaustion increases. This implies that level of emotional exhaustion is different for different employees depending upon the

nature of the work and duties performed. Among nursing staff major determinants of emotional exhaustion are increased job demands, use of technology, competition, work load, task autonomy and reduced advancement opportunities (Sabine, 2000). As emotional exhaustion can estimate the cumulative effects of work stressors that is why some of the sources of emotional exhaustion and job stress are same like high work load, role overload and pressure due to work.

The following figure is showing the emergence of emotional exhaustion as a dimension of burnout caused by job stress.

Job Stress and Employee Turnover

Job stress had deleterious effects on job satisfaction and employees level of turnover. Stress plays a very significant role in employees behaviour related to job like turnover (Sager, 1994). Role ambiguity (defined as lack of clear information about task and duties and performance outcomes expected) and role conflict (defined as lack of coincidences between roles and within roles) are the most frequently studied stressors in the job stress domain (Dowden & Tellier, 2004; Ouyang, 2009). Role ambiguity creates role stress it can be a consequence of misunderstanding about job expectation and how to achieve expected job outcome and eventually leads to employee leaving the job. The propensity to leave an organization is also manifested when there is experience of lack of information for performing job duties properly or when the expected outcomes are ambiguous or due to high workload. These things may increase employee’s propensity to leave because they feel less involved less satisfied and undergo stress. Employees having feeling of insecurity of job and having similar job status cause stress and leads to quitting of job. M. Imran et al in 2013 reveal that as job stress increases, employee’s intention to turnover increases.

As stress have toughed almost all profession and obviously leads to leaving the job. It is identified by researchers that job stress have cost million dollars to the organization all over the world and the costs are due to turnover, higher rate of absenteeism, low performance and health care (Tett & Meyer, 1993). Several researchers had revealed that the factors that lead to job related stress (stressors) influences employees to leave the organization. Core stressors reduce the job satisfaction and commitment and hence increase employee turnover (Miller & Frith, 2006).

High level of absentees and turnover are always associated with stressful working roles (ACA Research Pty, Sydney). An employee’s satisfaction level is also deviated towards dissatisfaction because of less secured job environment and less job security and lack of procedural justice which leads to job related stress and hence increases employees intention to turnover (Firth et al., 2007).

As discussed earlier that reason of turnover are not organizational centred only because they depends upon the economic condition of the business environment and also upon the financial condition of an individual. Bad financial condition of an employees will create stress and in order to overcome this stress he/she will try to leave current job and search for a job offering better pay (Mano & Shay 2004).

Chaturani & Sangarandanya in 2008 studied the relationship of job stress and turnover of no managerial employees in garment industry of Sri Lanka and found a positive co-relationship between them. Nasrin & Hojat in 2013 also manifested a positive relationship between job stress and employee turnover. Occupational stress is considered as job stress in an organizational context. (Ahmed et.al, 2014) and turnover is predicted by two factors influenced by organizational stress and that are job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Lack of

organizational commitment leads to employee turnover. A positive relationship was found by Ali M. 2013 while studying the occupational stress and turnover intention in nursing staff. A positive relationship is also revealed by Ahmed, S et al. in 2014 between job stress as independent variable and turnover of employee as dependent variable over a diverse field of professionals, he found that when pressures overcome workers which are common to their field, they workers change careers in order to decrease job stress. So we can hypothesize that job stress has a positive impact on employee turnover.

H1: Job stress has a positive relationship with employee turnover.

Job Stress and Emotional Exhaustion

Job stress and emotional exhaustion are very common phenomena of workplace they have a very strong relationship. Muhammad Owais 2015 studied the relationship of job satisfaction and emotional exhaustion and he found that they have an inverse relationship and as mentioned above that job satisfaction is one factor of job stress so as job satisfaction decreases, job stress increases and hence emotional exhaustion increases. Mohsen G et al. in 2012 revealed that employees having job stress may be more emotionally exhaust with their job and may engage in deviant behaviours (workplace deviance can be defined as that voluntary behaviour that violates institutionalized norms and in doing so threatens the wellbeing of the organization). Stress first induced non-equilibrium state in the human system, and then motivate them to strive to return the previous equilibrium. Some people for returning equilibrium, if simultaneously experience the negative emotions (e.g., emotional exhaustion), will become ready to engage in deviant behaviours (Golparvar & Hosseinzadeh, 2011). Sabine S, (2001) also found a positive relation between job stress and emotional exhaustion of employees at workplace. Job stress or burnout is a strong predicator of emotional exhaustion.

H2: Job stress has a positive relationship with emotional exhaustion.

Research Methology

The framework of this research is as follows:

Research Framework

Research Design

The research design of this study is descriptive. Descriptive research describes any event, phenomenon, state or incident, it helps in describing salient features of sample under research (Nadeem, 2005). Descriptive researches only describes the existing condition and it does not make any judgments (Creswell, 1994). The main purpose of this descriptive research is that it will confirm that hypothesis developed in the above section will reveal the current situation of the variables constructs it does not make any inference or does not predict any future situation and this method is also in accordance with the past research related to this topic.

Research Method

The research method adapted is survey technique. Where survey is a quantitative research method which uses questionnaires or structured interviews for the purpose of data collection from a sample of specific population with an intent to generalize the results from sample to population (John W. Creswell, 2009) and where sample is a representative part of population usually smaller in size then population (Nadeem, 2005). Questionnaire used for collection of data is actually a list of questions pertaining to the objective of the study (Nadeem, 2005).

Sample

The sample for the purpose of data collection is selected through the technique of simple random sampling which can be defined as drawing a sample in such a way that each and every element of the population bears an equal chance of being selected for the sample (Nadeem, 2005).

The sample for this study were the employees from government as well as private organization of Peshawar Pakistan. Self-administered questionnaires were distributed by hand to employees of all hierarchy and positions including, managers, non-managers, supervisors and technicians having job tenure of more than a year and having some basic know how of the model variables. The employees were of Institute of Management Studies (Government), Institute of Management Sciences (Semi Government), Intellisense (Private), Multibiz Service (Private) and Advance Telecom Customer Care (Private). Selection of sample is based from the knowledge of past research. At total 250 questionnaires were distributed that is 50 to each organization out of which 121 were responded back giving a response rate of 80.67% which is acceptable in comparison to previous research. Care was taken about the confidentiality of data collected and it was assured to the respondents that the intention of data collection is for completion of research study only, with no other intention of using it against any respondent personally and/or professionally. One hour was given for the completion of questionnaire, and were collected back by hand on the same time. Needed assistance was provided to all respondents in filling questionnaire on the spot.

Scales and Variables

For collecting the data about the demographic profile of employees, scales of age, gender, designation, job tenure, income were included in the questionnaire. The other three variables of current study are explained below with the help of pervious research and questionnaires.

Job Stress

Job stress was the first variable incorporated in the study. In the research model job stress is performing the role of independent variable. For collecting information about it first four items were taken from Beehr et al. 2001. The 5th item measuring the job stress caused by role ambiguity was taken from House and Rizzo (1972). Respondents were asked to indicate how often an item was a source of stress on a 5-point scale with anchors, 5 = always and 1= never. More the scale represents more stress.

Employee Turnover

Employee turnover was incorporated in the research model as dependent variable. Item number 6th to 9th were included from Bluedorn 1982 for measuring it. And the 10th item of questionnaire measuring turnover was taken from Camman, Fichman, Jenkins, & Klesh (1979). Responses were taken on a 5-point scale with anchors, 5 = always and 1= never.

Emotional Exhaustion

The second dependent variable of the research model was emotional exhaustion. The 11th item included in the questionnaire for measuring it was taken from Mulki et al 2006. Last five items measuring emotional exhaustion were adapted from one of the three subscales of Maslach Burnout Inventory from Maslach, Jackson and Leiter (1996). This scale is been recognized as a leading measure of burnout for a decade. This scales was designed to measure the three dimension of burnout namely emotional exhaustion, personal accomplishments and depersonalization. (Discussed in literature review). Originally it has 21 items but the items measuring only emotional exhaustion are incorporated in this questionnaire. The results obtained were analysed through regression analysis mentioned in following section.

Analysis

Results were analysed using SPSS 16.0. Descriptive statistic measures of frequency were used for the variables revealing the personal and demographic characteristics of the respondent and regression analysis was run for

measuring the latent variable. Firstly job stress (independent variable) was regressed with employee turnover (dependent variable), then the same independent variable as regressed with the other dependent variable that is emotional exhaustion. The same procedure was followed for measuring the results for private and public sector separately.

Reliability Analysis of Model Variables

The reliability analysis was computed using scale of Cronbach's alpha. Which showed that all variables in our study were more than acceptable and recommended value 0.50 by Nunnally (1970) and 0.60 by Moss et al. (1998). This shows that all the 16 items were reliable and valid to measure the impact of job stress on employee turnover and emotional exhaustion. Values are showed in table below:

Table 1

Reliability Analysis of Model Variables

No.	Variables	Item	Reliability
1	Job Stress	5	0.731
2	Employee Turnover	5	0.796
3	Emotional Exhaustion	6	0.851

Results

Respondent's profile

Information of the respondents about personal and demographic factors were collected under the heads of gender, age, job title, income, tenure and status from the questionnaire. The categories for the variables of age and income were made according to the lowest and highest limit obtained by the respondent. The descriptive analysis of these variables are presented in table below:

Table 2

Profile of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	75	62.0
	Female	46	38.0
	Total	121	100.0
Age	21-25	33	27.3
	26-30	23	19.0
	31-35	65	53.7
	Total	121	100.0
	Managerial	23	19
Job Title	Non Managerial	86	71.1
	Others	12	9.9
	Total	121	100.0
Job Tenure	1 year or more	91	75.2
	2 year or more	30	24.8
	Total	121	100.0
Income	15000 and above	86	71.1
	30000 and above	35	28.9
	Total	121	100.0
Marital Status	Married	42	34.7
	Unmarried	79	65.3
	Total	121	100.0

Out of these 121 respondents 43 were from government (18 female and 25 male) sector and 78 (female 26 and male 52) from private sector.

Hypothesis Testing

The first hypothesis of the research was:

H1: Job Stress has a Positive Relationship with Employee Turnover

The results of the present research shows that a significant positive relationship exists between the independent variable job stress and dependent variable employee turnover. This significant positive relationship is revealed by the value of beta (β) which equals to 0.515 and p equals to 0.000. These values implies that job stress can cause about 51.5% change in employee turnover. Which is a very strong impact because 1% change in job stress will bring about 51% change in employee turnover. So these results confirms the validity of our first hypothesis and we conclude that job stress has a positive effect on employee turnover. But if we consider both sectors individually then the results are quite interesting that the value of beta (β) equals to 0.39 where p equals to 0.000 and in case of private sector the value for beta (β) equals to 0.68 where p equals to 0.000. These values clearly shows that in government sector, employees does not leaves a job as quickly as due to job stress as in private sector due to many other factors.

The second hypothesis of the research was:

H2: Job Stress has a Positive Relationship with Emotional Exhaustion

The results of the present research shows another significant and positive relationship between independent variable job stress and the second dependent variable emotional exhaustion. This positive and significant result is also manifested by examining the value of beta (β) which equals to 0.571 and p equals to 0.000. These values shows that about 57% change in emotional exhaustion is caused by job stress. This also a very strong impact as 1% change in job stress will lead to 57% change in emotional exhaustion. So these results confirms the validity of our second hypothesis as well and we conclude that job stress has a positive relationship with emotional exhaustion. But when these variables are regressed separately for public and private sector, the results obtained were a bit different. Value of beta (β) for public sector is quite less than private sector i.e. 0.28 and for private is 0.55. So this separate analysis shows that employees of private sector are more emotionally exhausted as compare to the employees of public sector in our sample.

Regression Results

This table shows the results of the regression analysis of the latent variables combine for public and private sector. It does not include the values of estimate separately for both sectors:

Table 3

Hypothesis	Model Variable	Estimate	Standard Error	Results
H1	Job stress with employee turnover	0.515	0.093	Supported
H2	Job stress with emotional exhaustion	0.571	0.054	Supported

Research framework with values:

Discussion

As mentioned earlier the most crucial objective of the study is to find out the impact of stress due to job on employee turnover and emotional exhaustion. The current research is highlighting the association between job stress and employee’s behaviour on work place like turnover and feeling of emotional exhaustion. Furthermore the research can influence the employee and employer as well and there activities on workplace. Previous researches and current study fully supports the relationship between job stress, employee turnover and emotional exhaustion. And this relationship can vary as the selection of sample changes because all workplaces have different stress factors and there intensities also vary from one place to other. The relationship between job stress

and employee turnover varies depending upon the economic condition of the country. If there are more job opportunities then small level of stress will lead to turnover immediately, and if there are less job opportunities then even with stress the employees will not leave their job immediately. It is also shown from the results of this research that employee turnover due to stress is more intense in private sector as compared to public sector. Employees in public sector are less emotionally exhausted and are less leaving the job due to job stress, their reason may be the incentives offered in government sector or less workload or other factors like that including reputation and grade too. But in private sector one cannot enjoy these charms that why with less increment in job stress leads to turnover and emotional exhaustion. Hence we can conclude that job stress in public sector is more as compared to private sector.

Practical Implication

According to the results of the present research, it is shown that the variables incorporated in this study are quite important for predicting employee behaviour and overall organizational productivity. To check the level of stress from different factors especially factors that are related to job and task and its effect on employees level of emotional exhaustion and employee turnover in different private and public organizations and institutions, this research may be helpful. In Pakistan the end result of this research had managerial implications for management department of every business. This research will give them the awareness about the relationship of job stress and its impact on emotional exhaustion and employee turnover and they should try stress level among employees to control turnover and other employee behaviours which are outside the scope of this research, but, are important.

Limitations and Future Recommendations

The data is collected from the respondents of same geographical area and that is Peshawar. Although the employees were from different organizations of different sectors but to some extent they all are having same culture values and attitude towards work and other things. The stress factors which are extra organizational like political, economic and financial conditions are almost the same. More significant results can be obtained if the data may be collected from more diversified industries and areas. As culture play a very important role in the findings of the study. Cultural psychologists suggest that national culture differences had an influence on employee decision making and evaluation. (Lok and Crawford, 2004; Lau and Ngo, 1996) The results can be more beneficial for managers if the factors of job stress would have been included in the research model and then its impact would have been included.

So the limitations of the research are considering limited area for data collection and no consideration of sources or factors creating job stress in research model.

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